

Improving the methods of analyzing the impact of the use of digital technologies on economic growth in industrial enterprises

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Abstract: This article is devoted to determining the impact and evaluation of the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) on the economic growth of the economies of Central Asia. In order to empirically study the impact of various ICT indicators on economic growth, panel group data was used. At the same time, the per capita GDP, which reflects the pace of economic development, is the effective indicator (function). Studies and analysis have shown that indicators of the economic development of ICTs are one of the key factors of economic growth in Central Asia. The results of the study indicate that the use of ICT in the countries of Central Asia has a positive and significant impact on their economic growth.

Keywords: IT, economic growth, group data, Central Asian Countries, analysis, independent variables.

Introduction

In the last two decades, the significant development of information and communication technologies (ICT) has led several scholars to consider its impact on the economy, especially on release has sparked interest in analyzing the role of ICT in poverty reduction. Most of the research conducted in this field found that ICT is one of the important factors of economic and social development. The purpose of this article is to analyze the relationship between ICT and economic growth in five Central Asian countries over a period of 19 years. This study empirically investigates how ICTs affect economic growth rates in terms of GDP per capita. In addition, several macroeconomic variables were used to show the effect on GDP per capita growth. This article has attempted to find a link between information and communication technologies and economic growth in recent years for at least two reasons. First, this study is one of the first to analyze the relationship between ICT and economic growth in Central Asia, while there are no studies that analyze the impact of ICT on specific countries (Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan). Second, the impact of ICT on economic growth has been studied using two main and very important different indicators, whereas other studies for developing countries have used one or two ICT indicators. The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews recent empirical studies examining the impact of ICT on national economic growth. Section 3 presents the data and indicators used with reference to the empirical method.

Literature Review

In recent decades, the impact of ICT on the level of economic growth has been studied by a number of researchers at the level of a country or group of countries, using different methods, data sets and different time periods. Most of the empirically analyzed studies have found that the use of ICT leads to an increase in the country's GDP per capita, employment and labor productivity. According to a study by the World Economic Forum, a 10% increase in the ICT sector in a country leads to a 0.76% increase in per capita GDP and a 1.03% increase in employment. A study by IHRT showed that ICT is leading the way in reducing poverty by creating new jobs and sources of income,

as well as reducing spending on health and education for the poor. As stated by the World Bank, ICT consists of "hardware, software, networks and means of collecting, storing, processing, transmitting and presenting information (voice, data, text, images)". ICT stands for "digital telephone network, mobile phones, internet access, internet servers and fixed broadband network, as well as other technologies" [1]. Many researchers argue that ICT is important for the rapid growth of the economy in many ways: ICT use allows users to quickly access knowledge and information; Information and communication technologies facilitate and accelerate the communication of companies, in this way they reduce production costs and increase efficiency [2]; ICT enables access to new markets, reduces capital costs by improving the efficiency of financial markets [3]; The use of ICT and even the use of the Internet alone can improve any business by reducing agency costs and changing information asymmetry [4]. Published results show that an 11 percent increase in Internet use increases trade exposure by 3.9 percent, which in turn increases economic development by 0.18 percent. Salahuddin and Gow studied the effects of internet usage, financial growth and trade transparency on economic growth [5]. The obtained results showed a significant and positive correlation between these indicators over a long period of time. In addition, the impact of Internet use on the company's activities was studied. Accordingly, [6]. Investigated the external financing opportunities of Internet-based commercial companies and organizations. The results of the study showed that the use of the Internet is one of the main factors that ease the financial difficulties of companies that have access to external financing, so that using the internet helps small businesses grow steadily [7]. Scientists say that the use of the Internet also allows external financing of large projects, so the use of the Internet improves social security. Information and communication technologies The importance of the effect has been studied and analyzed by many scientists. Nibel assessed the impact of information and communication technologies on the economic development of 59 low-income, high-income, and rapidly developing countries over a 6-year period. The results of the research had a significant impact on the economic development of the analyzed countries [8]. Moreover, the evaluations for these three country groups showed little difference between them. After analyzing the results, the researcher noted that, compared to developed countries, low-income and rapidly developing countries do not benefit much from the financing of information and communication technologies. The purpose of conducting this study and its specific features is that there are no research, development or scientific articles that analyze the negative relationship between ICT and economic growth in Central Asian countries such as Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan[9]. Thus, considering the need for literature, analysis and results, this study was carried out. In addition to the existing literature, the paper examines two key and very important explanatory indicators of the impact of ICT on economic growth in these developing countries. used[10]. Many researchers have studied the impact of ICT on economic growth, mainly by dividing countries into two types, such as developed and developing countries. Thus, the obtained results show that the impact of ICT on economic growth is greater in developed countries than in developing countries. This study was conducted to find a clear answer to this question on the example of the Central Asian countries.

Materials and methods

Statistical observation, grouping, descriptive, systematic analysis and econometric modeling methods were used in the research. This study assesses the impact of several ICT factors on economic growth in 5 Central Asian countries, namely Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan, over a 19-year period. The analysis included 10 variables that performed group data. They are taken from the "international development indicators" database of the World Bank. In the used econometric models, economic growth is the dependent variable and is determined by the GDP per capita (at the current US dollar exchange rate and SOQP). Two types of explanatory variables are used in the econometric model, firstly, the main explanatory variables, they consist of two different ICT indicators (percentage of fixed broadband subscriptions and internet users per 100 people); The

second group of descriptive variables consists of economic variables for management (accumulation of gross fixed capital, inflation rate, unemployment rate, open trade, foreign direct investment and public expenditure on final consumption). The following two methods describe panel data studies. Group data (panel data) consists of repeated observations of the same measurement units. In this case, they are made up of selected countries. The current group data is balanced because the period is the same for all countries. The study allows for inclusion of group data, controlling for unobservable and unmeasurable variables, in particular: cultural factors among selected countries. It is also preferable to apply group data to variables that change over time. But applying them from one region to another is not very effective. When analyzing group data using a Fixed Effects model, the explanatory variables are assumed to be random. The term "permanent effect estimate function" is used to define the estimate in the parameters of the regression model. The fixed effects model is commonly used to analyze the degree of exposure to different parameters. This method examines the negative correlation between independent variables and outcome data given in the same measurement units. Each state has its own characteristics that can affect independent parameters. There is an assumption that, in the implementation of the sustainable effect model, the determining factors are influenced by specific characteristics. You should definitely check it out. It is known that there is a relationship between the independent variables and the magnitude of the error. Fixed effects methods are used to isolate the effects of these characteristics of the independent variables. One of the main principles of the sustainable impact model is that all these methods have different effects for each region. Because each country is different, the margin of error does not change. It should be considered that the fixed effects model is used to study the causes of changes in any selected countries. An overview of the Random Effect model is based on the assumption that differences between countries are random and unrelated to the independent variables used in the model. According to Green, the main difference between fixed and random effects is the relationship between the individual effect and the independent variable in the model, and the effect on the independent variable can be random or correlated. One of the advantages of the method is the presence of an independent variable with random effects in the model. In fixed effects models, all these variables are constant terms. As Gujarati points out, standard stationary tests are usually very large data was intended for the set, and since the sample size of the data realized was not so large, stationary tests were not used.

Results

This article examines the impact of information and communication technologies on economic growth in 5 Central Asian countries using group data for 19 years. Regression probabilities and several tests recommended by the empirical econometric literature were tested to select the model with the best impact of ICT on economic growth. Description tables and conclusions are given for the performed tests. The results of descriptive analysis, tests and statistics showed that all the selected variables have positive values, but not all of them are considered significant for the selected time. The general result of the study showed that each of the selected indicators meets all the requirements of the group analysis.

Multicollinearity detection test The main purpose of regression analysis is to isolate the relationship between each of the independent and dependent variables. The general view of the regression coefficient is that it estimates the average change in the dependent variable for each change in the independent variable, holding every other independent variable constant. The last part is very important for testing multicollinearity.

The value of one of the independent variables may not be changed by the others, but if the independent variables are related to each other, this means that the change in one of the variables is related to the movement of the other variables. If the correlation between the variables is strong, then it becomes more problematic to make changes to the variables. Because the independent variables tend to change harmonically, it is usually difficult for the model to estimate the negative correlation between the independent and dependent variables.

Multicollinearity multicollinearity— if the model uses other terms is created, this type of multicollinearity is generated. More precisely, it is the result of a model that is assigned but does not itself exist. Data multicollinearity— artificially to this category model more data will exist by itself than added. Observational analyzes reflect these types of problems. The analysis of the entire test showed that there is no significant correlation between the independent variables selected for the analysis of the economic growth of information and communication technologies in Central Asia. Here, the main ICT indicators are found between the control variable (fixed broadband subscription) and the dependent variable (GDP per capita) with the highest correlation. In this case, the correlation is 0.5397, which is normal. The highest correlation between GDP per capita and percentage of internet users is 0.584. The variables used for economic control do not have the problem of multicollinearity with economic growth. Hausman test. Given the nature of the data obtained, the study used group analysis and had to choose a fixed or random effect model for analysis. Thus, the Hausman test was used. A test can be used to evaluate a model selected using endogenous independent variables. Therefore, endogenous indicators follow a system of uniform equations. If the independent variable is endogenous in the applied models, the linear regression method will be computationally useless due to the violation of the theory of least squares, that is, there will be no correlation between the error value and the explanatory indicator. In this case, instrumental indicators are used as an alternative to process evaluation. In the process of analyzing group data, the Hausman test helps to choose a random or fixed effects model. If the null hypothesis is accepted, then the random effects method is used, otherwise the fixed effects method is used. The results of the Hausman test indicated that the model with fixed effects could be used in the current analyzes as the probability level was lower than 0.05.

Heteroskedasticity modified test also has another name, Wald chi-square test, this test is used to determine the significance of explanatory variables in the model being implemented. A "significant" effect means that the variable contributes to the model being changed, ensuring that nothing is left out without the variable having an effect in the model. This test is used in a variety of models, including both binary and continuous variables. Rejecting the null hypothesis means that the variable in the equation can be omitted without affecting the model.

If the test shows that the variables for a particular indicator are equal to zero, then it means that the indicator can be removed from the corresponding model. If the test finds that the indicators have an effect, then it should add the indicator to the model. This test is usually compared to chi-square because the sampling distributions are known. A version of this test is sometimes called the "Wald chi-square test" to distinguish it from the "Linear Logarithmic Wald ChiSquare Test". The "log-linear Wald chi-square test" is not a parameter type that focuses on the ratio of logarithmic coefficients. To determine whether there is a correlation between variables, a modified Wald test was performed. The modified Wald test analyzed the sample group data and showed that the results fit all the selected models and data, that there was no correlation between the selected parameters, and that they were all independent of each other. Thus, they do not violate the linear regression probabilities, since each variable less than 1 implies no correlation between the variables. This means that the model, data and variables used are all important. The results are presented in Appendix 3. Wooldridge's "autocorrelation" test. Selected after several years autocorrelation can be expressed mathematically to describe the degree of similarity between a time interval and itself. The same thing happens when calculating the negative correlation between different time intervals. They are used twice during the trial period.

Discussions

After analysis and testing, the test results found showed that there is no correlation between the selected variables. This proves that the sampled data and variables are independently relevant and significant. Correlation matrix of test residuals. On the selected model information and communication technologies using the correlation matrix of test residuals to show the independence

of variables in order to describe causal relationships between selected countries, group data were tested.

Test results for the value of all explanatory and control variables showed that it was below 1.00. This means that there is no correlation between the variables and they are completely independent of each other. Pesaran's test of cross-sectional independence. Pesaran cross-sectional independence test is used to analyze whether variables are correlated between states. If there is a problem of cross-sectional dependence, it will lead to distortions in the test results. Thus, to see if the problem exists, a cross-sectional Pesara independence test was conducted. The results showed that there is no cross-sectional problem in the data as the probability is 0.6208. The obtained result confirmed that it corresponds to the data of the selected group and meets all the requirements. Variance enhancement factor test (DKO). Dispersion enhancer used to detect multicollinearity in factor regression analysis. The problem of multicollinearity occurs when there is a correlation between the variables in the applied model. If this problem is present, it can negatively affect the regression results and the test performance, how much the multicollinearity problem affects the regression variance in the chosen model. Thus, this variance boosting factor test was used to avoid the problem of multicollinearity and avoid data bias. As a result, the results presented in Appendix 7 were published. The obtained results show that there is no problem of multicollinearity in the model, which negatively affects the regression results. Regression analysis is a very useful statistical technique is, and the method used allows to check the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. There are many types of regression analysis and all of them have a common picture of studying the effect of one or more independent variables on the dependent variable. A regression test was conducted to find out how much the effect of the independent variables on the variable from the research and the following results were obtained. Since all variables in the data are obtained as percentages, the description is also given in percentages. Madden and Savage analyzed data from 28 developed countries of the European Union in the period on the correlation of foreign direct investment with economic development. The results of the study showed a positive correlation between the indicators. The obtained data revealed that FDI has a positive but insignificant effect on GDP per capita in developing countries. Therefore, while the Central Asian countries are developing, foreign direct investment has a positive but insignificant effect on GDP per capita. The results of the analysis showed a positive and significant effect of ICT in all selected countries, but this effect may be stronger for developing countries. Econometric evaluation showed a positive and significant effect of foreign investment on developed countries, but in developing countries this effect is positive, but is irrelevant. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. The impact of fixed subscriptions on broadband has been studied and analyzed by Chernich et al.

Studies have shown a positive and significant impact of ICT on economic growth. The article discusses the impact of fixed broadband infrastructure on economic growth. Analyzed for the period for 25 member states of the Economic Cooperation Organization. The results showed that a 10 percent increase in broadband access could lead to a 0.9 to 1.5 percent increase in GDP per capita. In this case, a one percent increase in broadband leads to a 0.166 percent increase in GDP per capita, holding all other variables constant. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. Changeable inflation showed a positive and significant effect. In individual countries of Central Asia, a one percent increase in inflation leads to a 0.22 percent increase in GDP per capita, holding all other parameters constant. Thus, a one percent increase in the number of Internet users leads to a 0.22 percent increase in GDP per capita, all else being equal. A 1 percent increase in trade transparency under open trade conditions leads to an increase in GDP per capita of 1.6069 percent. As for consumption and unemployment costs, a 1 percent increase in each variable leads to a 0.12241 and 0.1603 percent decrease in GDP per capita, respectively, holding all else constant. Meiyers whether the internet has a direct effect on economic growth or an indirect effect through trade, tried to find out. The author used data for 162 countries.

Results of the multicollinearity test between the variables included in the regression

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. vif, uncentered
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Variable	VIF	1/VIF
capform	9.44	0.105920
ln_inf	4.02	0.248709
ln_interne~s	3.88	0.257611
ln_fdi	3.58	0.278946
ln_fsub	2.34	0.427909
cen_unemp	1.97	0.507850
cen_trade	1.56	0.640168
cen_conexp	1.28	0.782275
Mean VIF	3.51	

Figure 1. Source: author's development based on STATA software

And the results revealed that internet use has a positive and significant effect on economic growth, not directly but indirectly through trade. Thus, trade transparency contributes to economic growth more than any other variable. A 1 percent increase in trade transparency leads to a 1.6069 percent increase in GDP per capita.

Conclusions

Having studied scientific research and systematized information, as well as comments and explanations given as a result of empirical research of economic literature, we were able to come to the following conclusions: 1. This research work covers 19 years. It aims to determine and empirically study the relationship between ICT development and economic growth in Central Asian countries. In this research paper, two main and very important six variables of economic management are used to explain ICT. Broadband subscriptions, percentage of internet users, direct foreign investment, inflation, trade openness, final consumption expenditure, unemployment and capital accumulation are independent variables. This scientific research is one of the first studies dedicated to the analysis and assessment of the relationship between ICT and economic growth in Central Asian countries (Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan). It is based on several tests and analyses, including multicollinearity detection test, Hausman test, modified Wald test for heteroskedasticity, Wooldridge's autocorrelation test, correlation matrix of test residuals, Pesaran's cross-sectional independence test, and variance boosting factor test.

2. The pace of development of ICT in Central Asian countries is not strong because it is not, M. Farhadi et al. focused on the data of 158 countries for 10 years and pointed out that the use of ICT is stronger for developed countries and weaker for low-income countries. Other researchers have also confirmed that the impact of ICT is not so strong for developing Results showed that there is a "bidirectional" negative relationship between the development of telecommunications and the level of economic growth. On the other hand, for low-income European countries, the negative correlation is generally one-sided. Thus, the researchers noted that the development of telecommunication networks is not an important indicator of the economic growth of developing countries. Empirical results and analysis of recent studies and research show that the development of ICT has a positive and significant impact on the GDP per capita. Thus, a one percent increase in ICT contributes to an

increase in GDP per capita of 0.1669 percent (broadband subscription) and 0.2218 percent (internet usage). The results obtained for economic indicators showed that inflation, trade openness, final consumption expenditure and unemployment have a significant impact on GDP per capita in Central Asia. Information and communication technologies, together with economic indicators, are an important part of economic development in Central Asian countries.

Acknowledgements

Based on the analysis and evaluation of this study, several recommendations can be made. To promote sustainable economic development, governments and politicians of Central Asian countries should focus more on increasing investment in the mobile communications sector, as this infrastructure is more cost-effective and profitable than landline phones. In addition, it is recommended that authorities encourage and expand the use of ICT for internet access and broadband. In order to improve and improve the effectiveness of the public administration system, authorities should use electronic government. In addition, they encourage the widespread use of ICT in private businesses and organizations, as well as reduce taxes, provide subsidies, improve e-commerce, should implement a number of reforms, such as the development of public-private partnerships for infrastructure and telecommunication services. In this regard, the Republic of Uzbekistan can serve as a positive example for the other four analyzed Central Asian countries. This year, at the suggestion of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 22.08.2022 No. PQ-357 in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and he paid special attention to the fact that for all of us, mastering modern knowledge, becoming the owner of true enlightenment and high culture should become a continuous vital need. He also noted that the development of ICT is a decisive factor in this regard. Since new, modern technologies and infrastructures give a strong impetus to the acceleration of development and the introduction of innovations, economic development, the widespread use of ICT is very important for the economic growth of Central Asian countries.

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